

Analysis of Suitable System and Dimensional Analysis for Integrated Bamboo Processing Machine

Dr. P. G. Mehar¹ Dr. A. V. Vanalkar² Dr. A. M. Badar³ V. D. Dhopte⁴ Dr. A. P. Ninawe⁵

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, K D K College of Engineering, Nagpur, 440024, M S, INDIA*

²*Department of Mechanical Engineering, K D K College of Engineering, Nagpur, 440024, M S, INDIA*

³*Department of Civil Engineering, K D K College of Engineering, Nagpur, 440024, M S, INDIA*

⁴*Department of Mechanical Engineering, K D K College of Engineering, Nagpur, 440024, M S, INDIA*

⁵*Department of Mechanical Engineering, K D K College of Engineering, Nagpur, 440024, M S, INDIA*

Abstract: In this research, the work carried out for obtaining suitable system of bamboo slicing. The various machines such as Hydraulic, Pneumatic and Mechanical bamboo processing machines are developed and the most suitable mechanism is finalized. Traditionally Cross cutting, splitting, slicing and stick making are the operations which is to be carried out by different machine. The bamboo processing machine consists of electric motor, driver pulley, driven pulley, belt, gear box, crank, connecting rod, slider, tool and structure. The mechanical design of above component is carried out using conventional design procedure. The objective of planning the experimentation is to obtain reliable and accurate results with the execution of minimum number of trials. Various methods of experimentation are developed to satisfy these objectives. In this research work identification of various parameter and dimensional analysis is carried out.

Keywords: Bamboo, Hydraulic, Pneumatic, Mechanical, Integrated, Analysis.

1.0 Analysis Of Suitable System:

In this the work carried out for obtaining suitable system of bamboo slicing is discussed. The various machines such as hydraulic, pneumatic and mechanical bamboo processing machines are developed and the most suitable mechanism is finalized.

1.1 Hydraulic Bamboo Processing Machine:

Traditionally, the splitting and slicing operations are performed on different machines. In this Hydraulic Bamboo processing machine both the operation are achieved in single machine. To perform above operation by a single machine, the special purpose dies are designed. To perform splitting, a splitting die is placed in the housing and the bamboo is to be placed in between the plunger and die. By actuating hydraulic system, the plunger moves down and push the bamboo against die. Due to shearing action, bamboo is splitted into number of pieces depending on the tool arranged in the die. Then to perform slicing, a slicing die is placed in housing and splitted bamboo is to be placed in between the plunger and die. By actuating hydraulic system, the plunger moves down and push the splitted bamboo against die. Due to shearing action, splitted bamboo used to get sliced into number of pieces depending on the tool arranged in the die.

Schematic of hydraulic bamboo processing machine is shown in figure 1.1. Hydraulic system consist of oil tank, vane pump, motor, check valve, pressure relief valve, directional control valve, throttle valve and hydraulic cylinder i.e. actuator. In this hydraulic system oil i.e. Enclova-48 is sucked in the vane pump which is operated by electric motor. The pressure of oil is then raised to 100 bar. The pressurized oil is then enters into the check valve which is one way valve which allows the pressurized flow in forward direction whereas the reverse flow is restricted. The pressurized oil then enters into the pressure relief valve. According the desired pressure of the system the pressure in the pressure relief valve is set. Thereafter, if the pressure in the system exceeds the set pressure the valve gets open and the excess oil returns in to the storage tank. The pressurized oil is then enters into directional control valve which is a four way valve viz. inlet port, outlet port and two power ports. The oil then enters into the throttle valve where one can adjust the speed of the actuator as per desire. Finally the pressurized oil enters into the double acting hydraulic cylinder wherein because of the pressurized oil piston moves. This way the hydraulic system works.

Figure 1.1: Schematic of Hydraulic Bamboo Processing Machine

In progressive die, both the operations, i.e. splitting and slicing are performed in a single stroke. In this die as shown below the distance of tool tip is denoted by T_1 and distance between the tool ends is denoted by T_2 . As the distance T_2 is lesser than T_1 , the slice gets stuck-up between two slicing tool.

Figure 1.2: Distance between two successive tools of splicing die

Figure 1.3: Progressive die

Advantages

- Unskilled operator can work on the machine.
- Two operations can be performed on the same machine like splitting and slicing.
- Machine is very easy to operate

- In combine die bamboo is jam because of insufficient space between cutting tools.
- Hydraulic systems are complicated.
- In this system hydraulic oils are used and hence there is always some oil leakage and floor get oily.

1.2 Pneumatic Bamboo Processing Machine:

The pneumatic bamboo processing machine is used to perform splitting and slicing operations in a single machine and in a single stroke. In this machine spring loaded work holder is used to hold the bamboo piece. Pneumatic cylinder is used to provide reciprocating motion to the work holder. The cutting blade is fixed along the path of reciprocating motion. In every stroke, the machine produces a bamboo slice. It eliminates the splitting operation.

Schematic of pneumatic bamboo processing machine is shown in figure 1.4. Pneumatic system consists of motor, air compressor, FRL unit (Filter-Regulator-Lubricator), directional control valve, throttle valve and double acting pneumatic cylinder. In compressor, air is compressed to 10 bar. The compressed air then enters into FRL unit i.e. Filter-Regulator-Lubricator where the compressed air gets filtered i.e. if there is any dust particle is there along with the compressed air they gets separated. If any one set the pressure of the system as 9 bar then that pressure of the compressed air is maintained. Similarly with the help of Lubricator, few oil particles get mixed with the compressed air during its flow. These oil particles helps in lubricating purpose for double acting pneumatic cylinder. This way the FRL unit works. The compressed air is then enters into the directional control valve where the direction of flow is decided. The compressed air is then enters into the throttle valve which helps in regulating the desired speed of the actuator. The compressed air then finally enters into double acting pneumatic cylinder where depending upon the direction of the flow of compressed air piston moves either forward or backward. This way pneumatic system works.

Figure 1.4: Schematic of Pneumatic Bamboo Processing Machine

Advantages

- Unskilled operator can work on the machine.
- Slice can produce without splitting operations.
- Machine is very easy to operate.
- Reduces time and cost.

Limitations

- Pneumatic systems are complicated.
- In pneumatic drives compressed air is used to compress piston since the air is compressible hence there is pressure variation.

1.3 Mechanical Bamboo Processing Machine

The mechanical bamboo processing machine is developed to overcome the limitations of hydraulic bamboo processing machine and pneumatic bamboo processing machine. In this machine slider crank mechanism is used to produce a bamboo slice. Electric motor is used as a prime mover. The belt drive is used to transmit the power from electric motor to the slider crank mechanism. In every stroke, the machine produces bamboo slices.

Figure 1.5: Mechanical Bamboo Processing Machine

Advantages

- Unskilled operator can work on the machine.
- Slice can produce without splitting operations.
- Reduces time and cost.

Limitations

- Less rigidity
- Excessive moving components
- Maintenance cost is more

1.4 Integrated Bamboo Processing Machine

Machine consists of electric motor which is used as a prime mover of the machine. The motor power is transmitted to the mechanical system with the help of V-belt drive. The gear box is used to reduce the use of multiple belt drives. The gear box is having gear ratio of 40:1. The work holder consists of pressure adjusting spring arrangement for providing the flexibility in bamboo sizes. The work piece holder reciprocates in guide way for providing the cutting motion to the bamboo. The cutting tool is fixed along the path of reciprocating motion.

Figure 1.6: Integrated Bamboo Processing Machine

The integrated bamboo processing machine is having various advantages, some of them discussed below.

- Final product is obtained in a single stroke.
- Machine is compact and robust in construction.
- Manufacturing cost of machine is low.
- No need of skilled workers.
- The arrangement is safe and simple.
- Power requirement is low as compare to previous machine.
- Only one man can operate the machine.
- It is preferable for household business.
- Space requirement is low compared to bamboo processing unit.
- Economically preferable.
- Maintenance cost is low.

Hence the integrated bamboo processing machine is selected for the further analysis.

2.0 Design of Mechanical Components:

The bamboo processing machine consists of electric motor, driver pulley, driven pulley, belt, gear box, crank, connecting rod, slider, tool and structure. The mechanical design of above component is made up of conventional design procedure [38] [39] [40]. using ASM, ASTM hand books, PSG data book etc. while designing any system the general design consideration are essentially to be taken into consideration and these are as below.

2.1 General Design Consideration

- a) Strength
- b) Reliability
- c) Thermal consideration
- d) Corrosions
- e) Wear
- f) Frictions
- g) Processing
- h) Utility
- i) Cost
- j) Safety
- k) Noise
- l) Weight
- m) Shape
- n) Size
- o) Flexibility
- p) Control
- q) Stiffness
- r) Surface finish
- s) Lubrications
- t) Maintenance
- u) Volume

2.2 Estimation of Force to Cut Slice From The Bamboo

The shear stress of bamboo is 2.2 N/mm² [30]. As per statistical records related to bamboo the maximum diameter of bamboo is 100mm and minimum diameter is 30 mm. Considering shearing action for separating the slice from bamboo, the cutting force require to separate the slices is as below.

$$a) \quad \tau = \frac{P}{A}$$

$$P = \tau \times A$$

$$P = 2.2 \times 100 \times 1$$

$$P = 220 \text{ N}$$

Where,

τ = shear stress, N/mm²

P = Cutting force, N

w = width of slice, mm

t = Thickness of slice, mm

b) Considering maximum diameter of bamboo as 100 mm and length of bamboo as 255 mm the dimension of trolley are as below

Width of trolley = 105mm

Length of trolley = 260mm

And as per the readily available thickness of plate, the thickness selected is $t = 5$ mm thus weight of first plate = volume \times density

$$\begin{aligned} &= (260 \text{ mm} \times 110 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm} \times 7800) / (1000)^3 \\ &= 1.115 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly weight of another parallel plate = 1.115 kg

Weight of 3rd plate and 4th plate = volume \times density

$$\begin{aligned} &= 105 \times 110 \times 5 \times 7800 / (1000)^3 \\ &= 0.45 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

Thus total weight of all 4 plates is = 1.115 + 1.115 + 0.45 + 0.4 kg

$$\begin{aligned} &= 3.13 \text{ kg} \\ &= 3.13 \times 9.81 \\ &= 30.7 \text{ N} \end{aligned}$$

C) Weight of bamboo having maximum diameter is 100 mm and length is 255 mm as per the reference is 1kg i.e. = 10 N

Hence the entire process force = $a + b + c$

$$= 220 + 30.7 + 10 = 260.7 \text{ N}$$

2.3 Static Force Analysis of Crank and Slider Mechanism and Estimation of Motor Power:

Analysis of suitable system it was concluded that simple crank and slider mechanism is most suitable for bamboo processing operation. Thus static force analysis for the crank and slider mechanism is carried out and there by all the joint forces and input torque is estimated.

O₁A = 2.8 cm
 AB = 6.8 cm
 Angle O₁AB = 30°

Scale For Space Diagram : 1cm = 50 mm

Space Diagram

Scale For Force Diagram: 1cm = 50 N

Force Diagram

$$F_{34} = -F_{43} = F_{32} = -F_{23} = 285 \text{ N} = +F_{12}$$

$$T_2 = F_{23} \times h$$

$$= 285 \times 0.05 \text{ Nm}$$

$$= 14.25 \text{ Nm}$$

$$\approx 15 \text{ Nm}$$

$$P = 5.21 \text{ cm}$$

$$= 260.7 \text{ N}$$

$$F_{34} = 5.7 \text{ cm}$$

$$= 285 \text{ N}$$

$$F_{14} = 1.7 \text{ cm}$$

$$= 85 \text{ N}$$

Figure 2.1: Static Force Analysis

Thus input torque = 15 Nm

Considering speed of crank at 60 RPM the power available at crank is given by

$$= \frac{2\pi NT}{60}$$

$$= \frac{2 \times \pi \times 60 \times 15}{60}$$

$$= 94.25$$

$$= 95 \text{ Watt}$$

Considering 10 % frictional losses in between crack and gear box, the power available is 104 Watt.

Considering the frictional losses in the gear box as 10% the power available is 115 Watt. Considering the frictional losses in the motor as 10% the power available should be 127 Watt.

Considering the unknown forces, motor selected is of 367.5 Watt. i.e. 0.5 H.P. Hence 3 motor are selected to evaluate the performance of electric motor and these motors are 0.5 H.P., 1 H.P. and 2 H.P.

2.4 Design of Connecting Rod

Joint forces of the connecting rod and angular position of crank is 30° at which bamboo touches the cutting tool is given by P = 285 N, say for example 300 N the compressive stress/tensile stress for mild still at yield point is given by 218N/mm² as referred in design data book.

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma &= \frac{p}{A} \\ A &= p/\sigma \\ &= 300/27 \\ &= 11.11 \text{ mm}^2\end{aligned}$$

Therefore diameter is = 3.76 mm

Hence the safe diameter selected is 15 mm

2.5 Design of Pulley

2.5.1 Driver pulley

Driver pulley = 8 inch

In bamboo processing machine, diameter of driver pulley = 20 cm = 200 mm.

From design data book Table XV-8, selecting for power range of 0.35 - 3.5 KW

Width of belt = 13mm

From design data book Table XV-7

Material: Cast iron

Type of construction: Arm construction

I. No. of arm = 4

No. of set = 1

II. Rim Thickness(t)

$$\begin{aligned}t &= 0.25D^{0.5}+1.5 \\ &= 0.25 \times 200^{0.5}+1.5 \\ &= 5.03 \text{ mm}\end{aligned}$$

2.5.2 Driven pulley

Driven pulley = 5 inch

As per our machine, diameter of driver pulley = 12 cm = 120mm.

From design data book Table XV-8, selecting for power range of 0.35 - 3.5 KW

Width of belt = 13mm

From design data book Table XV-7

Material: Cast iron

Type of construction: Arm construction

I. No. of arm = 4

No. of set = 1

II. Rim Thickness(t)

$$t = 0.25D^{1.5}$$

$$= 0.25 \times 120^{0.5} + 1.5$$

$$= 4.23 \text{ mm}$$

2.6 Design of Belt

$$\text{Rated power } (P_r) = 2 \text{ H.P.}$$

$$= 2 \times 736$$

$$= 1472 \text{ W}$$

$$= 1.472 \text{ KW}$$

$$\text{Design power } (P_d) = 1.472 \times 1.1 \quad (1.1 = \text{Load factor Table XV-2})$$

Now, For 1.617 KW Selecting proper dimension from Design Data book Table XV-8

Designation-A

- I. Nominal Width = 13mm
- II. Nominal thickness = 8mm
- III. Recommended pulley Dia. = 75mm

Center distance between two pulleys

$$C = D_1 + D_2$$

$$= 200 + 120$$

$$= 320 \text{ mm}$$

Length of belt

$$L = \pi \times (R_1 + R_2) + 2 \times X + \frac{(R_1 - R_2)^2}{X}$$

$$= \pi \times (100 + 60) + 2 \times 320 + \frac{(100 - 60)^2}{X}$$

$$= 1470 \text{ mm.}$$

2.7 Design of Structure

- i. Weight of motor = 15.3 kg.
= 16 kg. (approx.)
- ii. Weight of pulley (2) = 2+1
= 3 Kg
- iii. Weight of gear box = 25.80 kg
- iv. Weight of Crank = 7.1 Kg
- v. Weight of slider = 3.13 kg
- vi. Weight of guide ways = 5 kg

Force exerted by

i) Motor = 16×9.81
 = 160 N

ii) Pulley = 3×9.81
 = 30 N

iii) Crank = 7.8×9.81
 = 78 N

iv) Gear box = 25.80×9.81
 = 258 N

v) Slider = 3.13×9.81
 = 31.3 N

vi) Guide ways = 5×9.81
 = 50 N

Total force exerted by all components

$$P = 160 + 30 + 78 + 258 + 31.3 + 50$$

$$= 607.3 \text{ N}$$

As the force is getting distributed over four legs (Column) of machine are subjected to the compressive force

$$P/4 = 607.3/4$$

$$= 151.82 \text{ N}$$

Material for Colum is C.I. SAE20 having ultimate compressive strength as

$$S_{uc} = 560 \text{ MPa}$$

Selecting Factor of safety as 8, $S_{uc} = 560/8$

$$= 70 \text{ MPa}$$

Now,

$$S_{uc} = P/A$$

$$A = P/S_{uc}$$

$$= 151.82^2/70$$

$$= 2.16 \text{ mm}^2$$

Cross section area of Plate = 4 cm^2

$$= 1600 \text{ mm}^2$$

Hence Colum is safe.

3.0 Fabrication of Experimental Set Up:

Bamboo processing machine consist of slider crank mechanism. Slider crank mechanism has mainly four links crank connecting rod. Important parts of bamboo processing machine are discussed in this.

3.1 Components of Integrated Bamboo Processing Machine:

3.1.1 Motor

An electric motor is an electric machine that converts electrical energy into mechanical energy by electromagnetic means. Mainly electric motors produce rotary force which is also known as torque. A single phase AC induction motor is use in Bamboo processing machine as power source mounted over a support provided at the base stand. For experimental purpose to test the cutting accuracy of machine we used three standardized motors of different power viz.0.5 HP, 1 HP, 2 HP.

R.P.M: 1440 (Driving shaft)

R.P.M: 36 (Driven shaft)

Figure 3.2: Electric motor

3.1.2 V belt drive

The power available at the output shaft of electric motor is to be transmitted to the gear box by means of V belt. Advantage of using v belt is to obtain perfect velocity ratio and further common phenomenon in flat belt drive like sleep i.e. movement of belt without carrying pulley is reduced. The machine consists of V belt drive with arm construction having bigger pulley dia. 8 inches, smaller pulley dia. 5 inches and center distance 49 cm.

Figure 3.3: V belt drive

3.1.3 Gear box

In bamboo processing machine a standard gear box is used for controlled transmission of power and stability. Gear box is mounted between driven pulley shaft and crank shaft. Objective of gear box is to reduce the rpm provided by standard electric motor without reducing torque, type of gear use in gear box is bevel gear and it transmits power in 90° between input and output shaft. The gear ratio is of 40:1.

Figure 3.4: Gear box

3.1.4 Crank

A Crank is a rotating machine arm attached at right angles to a rotating shaft or output shaft of gear box by means of pined joint. Another end of crank is pivoted to the connecting rod. In our machine particularly crank is a solid circular disc to serve dual purpose of flywheel as well as crank.

Material: Mild Steel

Mass of Crank = 7.05 kg.

Crank radius = 16 cm

Thickness = 8 mm

Figure3.5: Crank

3.1.5 Connecting rod

Connecting rod connects slider to the crank with pinned joint, to form simple mechanism to convert rotating motion to sliding motion. Connecting rod is a rigid mechanical element which transmits power from crank to slider without undergoing deformation. Effective length of connecting rod also determines the length of stroke. Generally the effective length of connecting rod is twice the length of radius.

Material Mild Steel

Mass of Connecting rod = 1.40 kg

Length of Connecting rod = 32 cm.

Figure 3.6: Connecting rod

3.1.6 Slider

Slider used in bamboo processing machine forms sliding pair with guide ways i.e. fixed link. One end of slider is connected to the connecting rod while other is fixed. Slider is made to slide inside the guide ways by means of small bearing supported inside the guide ways. Slider also act as a fixture for holding bamboo which holds bamboo inside it as it have hollow rectangular shape.

Material: Mild Steel

Mass: 5.406 kg

Length = 26 cm

Width = 9 cm

Height = 11 cm

Figure 3.7: Slider

3.1.7 Guide ways

Guide ways is an integral part of mechanism which is fully constrained, i.e. it's all degree of freedom are locked and made completely rigid by means of welding to the frame. Guide ways guides slider to slide inside it. Slider is having hollow rectangular parallelepiped shape.

Length = 62 cm

Width = 13 cm

Figure 3.8: CAD model of guide way

3.1.8 Frame

Frame (structure) is a stationary structure fabricated such that crank and slider mechanism and other component like motor, gear box and V belt drive can be easily mounted over it. Standard shape rectangular cross section angle made up of cast iron are used for the fabrication purpose.

Length = 90 cm

width = 51 cm

Height = 75 cm

Figure 3.9: CAD model of frame

3.1.9 Cutting tool

For any application of bamboo it must be cut accordingly. In bamboo cutting machine thin slices of bamboo can be produced by using proper cutting tool. The thickness of cutting tool is 6 mm, length of cutting tool is 32 cm and width is 12 cm. Bamboo cutting tool must have ability to withstand shear force required to split bamboo, so different material and cutting angles used are as follows.

Material	Relief angle	Rake angle
1) HcHcr	15 ⁰ 20 ⁰ 25 ⁰	0 ⁰ 2 ⁰ 4 ⁰
2) H.S.S	15 ⁰ 20 ⁰ 25 ⁰	0 ⁰ 2 ⁰ 4 ⁰
3) H.C.S	15 ⁰ 20 ⁰ 25 ⁰	0 ⁰ 2 ⁰ 4 ⁰

Figure 3.10: Cutting tool

Figure 3.11: Rake angle and relief angle of cutting tool

4.0 Experimental Investigation:

In this a attempt is made to design the experimental approach for gathering data to generate mathematical model for Bamboo processing operation. The bamboo processing is a complex phenomenon. There are many factors which causes the variation in output. The production rate, quality and efficiency are affected due to various input parameters.

4.1 Experimental Data Based Approach

The data of Bamboo processing is not known to the professionals involved in this type of operations. The quantitative relationship based on logic is not possible and hence the only alternative is of formulating experimental data based model.

The approach adopted for formulating generalized experimental data based model is suggested by Hilbert Schenck [32][33] as given below.

1. Identification of independent and dependent variables or quantities.
2. Reduction of independent variables adopting dimensional analysis.
3. Design of experimental set up.
4. Calibration of an instrument.
5. Measurement of experimental data.
6. Model Formulation
7. Optimization and validation
8. ANN simulation

The formulated model is an approximate generalized model. The Identification of dependent and independent variables of the phenomenon is to be carried out based on known qualitative physical phenomenon.

4.1.1 Methods of Experimentation

The objective of planning the experimentation is to obtain reliable and accurate results with the execution of minimum number of trials. Various methods of experimentation are developed to satisfy these objectives. Theories of experimentations [33] which are predominantly used in planning experimentations in engineering field are:

- 1) Factorial Experimentation
- 2) Classical Plan of Experimentation

Factorial Experimentation arrives at satisfactory result with reduced effort. This method is used where the nature of results is already known. This method is used for technically established process. Classical plan of experimentation requires maximum effort to get the reliable results, but the plan is generally applied when the process is technically unknown and sufficiently complex to develop an analytical model. In this case generally the interrelationship between the effect of controllable variables and environmental variables on the performance is not known. The research work attempts to establish empirical relationship between the Tool material, bamboo material and the dependent variables as production rate, quality and efficiency by performing experimental data collection by using factorial plan of experimentation.

4.2 Identification of Variables

The parameters which affect the production rate, quality and efficiency of an operation are selected. At preliminary stage, more parameters were selected based upon the material of bamboo and material of tool. Later on to reduce the variables in number, some variables are clubbed together while some variables which are seemed to be uncontrollable or least affecting, that parameter is rejected and finally a set of attributes were selected as follows:

Sr. No.	Variable	Types of Variable	Symbol	Dimensions
1	Tool Hardness	Independent	H_T	-
2	Relief Angle	Independent	ϕ	-
3	Condition of Bamboo	Independent	B_T	-
4	Rake Angle	Independent	α	-
5	Outer Diameter of bamboo	Independent	D_o	L
6	Inner Diameter of bamboo	Independent	D_i	L
7	Force	Independent	F	MLT^{-2}

LIBERTE JOURNAL (ISSN:0024-2020) VOLUME 14 ISSUE 5 2026				
8	Velocity	Independent	V_p	LT^{-1}
9	Input Energy	Independent	I_E	ML^2T^{-2}
10	Work Done	Independent	W_d	ML^2T^{-2}
11	Production Rate	Dependent	P_R	T^{-1}
12	Quality	Dependent	Q	-
13	Efficiency	Dependent	η	-

Table 4.1: parameters affecting Bamboo processing ac

4.3 Dimensional Analysis Using Buckingham's II Theorem:

Buckingham's π Method [33][34] is the methods of dimensional analysis. Buckingham π theorem states that "If there are n variables (independent and dependent variables) in a physical phenomenon and if these variables contain m fundamental dimensions (M, L, T) then the variables are arranged into (n-m) dimensionless terms. The arbitrary power of each variable can be decided by comparing the power of fundamental dimension on both sides of the equation. This way the relationship between dependent variables and independent variables can be evaluated [35].

The input parameters are as follows:

- 1) Tool Material Hardness, H_T
- 2) Relief Angle, ϕ
- 3) Type of Bamboo, B_T
- 4) Rake Angle, α
- 5) Outer Diameter of Bamboo, D_o
- 6) Inner Diameter of Bamboo, D_i
- 7) Force, F
- 8) Velocity, V_p
- 9) Input Energy, I_E
- 10) Work Done, W_d

The output parameters are as follows:

- 1) Production Rate, P_R
- 2) Quality/Angle of Curvature, θ
- 3) Efficiency, η

No. of variable available in the phenomenon, $n = 7$

No. of fixed dimension, $m = 3$

No. of π terms, $n - m = 4$

$$\pi_5 = D_o^a F^b V_p^c D_i$$

Power of m,

$$0 = 0 + b + 0$$

$$b = 0$$

Power of L,

$$0 = a + b + c + 1$$

$$0 = a + c + 1$$

Power of T,

$$0 = -2b - c$$

$$0 = -2 \times 0 - c$$

$$c = 0$$

Now, power of L,

$$0 = a + 0 + 1$$

$$a = -1$$

$$\pi_5 = D_o^{-1} F^0 V_p^0 D_i$$

$$\pi_5 = \frac{D_i}{D_o}$$

π_5 term related to outer diameter of bamboo

$$\pi_6 = D_o^a F^b V_p^c I_E$$

$$M^0 L^0 T^0 = (M^0 L^1 T^0)^a (M^1 L^1 T^{-2})^b (L^1 T^{-1})^c (M^1 L^2 T^{-2})$$

Power of M,

$$0 = b + 1$$

$$b = -1$$

Power of L,

$$0 = a + b + c + 2$$

$$0 = a - 1 + 0 + 2$$

$$a = -1$$

Power of T,

$$0 = -2b - c - 2$$

$$0 = -2 \times (-1) - c - 2$$

$$c = 0$$

$$\pi_6 = D_o^{-1} F^{-1} V_p^0 I_E$$

$$\pi_6 = \frac{I_E}{D_o F}$$

π_6 term related to input energy

$$M^0 L^0 T^0 = (M^0 L^1 T^0)^a (M^1 L^1 T^{-2})^b (L^1 T^{-1})^c (M^1 L^2 T^{-2})$$

Power of M,

$$0 = b + 1$$

$$b = -1$$

Power of L,

$$0 = a + b + c + 2$$

$$0 = a - 1 + 0 + 2$$

$$a = -1$$

Power of T,

$$0 = -2b - c - 2$$

$$0 = -2 \times (-1) - c - 2$$

$$c = 0$$

$$\pi_7 = D_o^{-1} F^{-1} V_p^0 W_d$$

$$\pi_7 = \frac{W_d}{D_o F}$$

π_7 term related to work done

$$\pi_8 = D_o^a F^b V_p^c P_R$$

$$M^0 L^0 T^0 = (M^0 L^1 T^0)^a (M^1 L^1 T^{-2})^b (L^1 T^{-1})^c (M^0 L^0 T^{-1})$$

Power of M,

$$0 = 0 + b + 0 + 0$$

$$b = 0$$

Power of L,

$$0 = a + b + c + 0$$

$$0 = a - 1$$

$$a = 1$$

Power of T,

$$0 = -2b - c - 1$$

$$0 = -c - 1$$

$$c = -1$$

$$\pi_8 = D_o^1 F^0 V_p^{-1} P_R$$

$$\pi_8 = \frac{D_o P_R}{V_p}$$

π_8 term related to production rate

$$\pi_9 = D_o^a F^b V_p^c \theta$$

$$M^0 L^0 T^0 = (M^0 L^1 T^0)^a (M^1 L^1 T^{-2})^b (L^1 T^{-1})^c (M^0 L^0 T^0)$$

Power of M,

$$0 = 0 + b + 0 + 0$$

$$b = 0$$

Power of L,

$$0 = a + b + c$$

$$a = 0$$

Power of T,

$$0 = -2b - c$$

$$c = 0$$

$$\pi_9 = D_o^0 F^0 V_p^0 \theta$$

$$\pi_9 = \theta \quad \pi_9 \text{ term related to quality}$$

$$\pi_{10} = \eta \quad \pi_{10} \text{ term related to efficiency}$$

$$\pi_1 = H_T \quad \pi_1 \text{ term related to hardness of tool}$$

$$\pi_2 = \emptyset \quad \pi_2 \text{ term related to relief angle}$$

$$\pi_3 = B_T \quad \pi_3 \text{ term related to types of bamboo}$$

$$\pi_4 = \alpha \quad \pi_4 \text{ term related to rake angle}$$

Sr. No.	Dimensionless Term	Non-Dimensional equation
1.	Term Related to hardness of tool material (π_1)	$\pi_1 = H_T$
2.	Term Related to relief angle (π_2)	$\pi_2 = \emptyset$
3.	Term Related to type of bamboo (π_3)	$\pi_3 = B_T$
4.	Term Related to rake angle (π_4)	$\pi_4 = \alpha$
5.	Term Related to outer diameter (π_5)	$\pi_5 = \frac{D_i}{D_o}$
6.	Term Related to energy input (π_6)	$\pi_6 = \frac{I_E}{D_o F}$

LIBERTE JOURNAL (ISSN:0024-2020) VOLUME 14 ISSUE 5 2026		
7.	Term Related to work done (π_7)	$\pi_7 = \frac{W_d}{D_o F}$
8.	Term Related to production rate (π_8)	$\pi_8 = \frac{D_o P_R}{V_p}$
9.	Term Related to quality (π_9)	$\pi_9 = \theta$
10.	Term Related to efficiency (π_{10})	$\pi_{10} = \eta$

Table 4.2: Dimensionless pi terms

4.4 Responses of an Activity

For the operation of bamboo processing the production rate, quality and efficiency [36] are considered as output. The study is conducted for four outputs

- Term related to Production Rate (Y_1) π_8
- Term related to quality (Y_2) π_9
- Term related to efficiency (Y_3) π_{10}

4.5 Causes of an Activity

According to calculated sample size, 1296 observations are collected and it is concluded that by taking all the parameters together in a summarized manner, the reduction of π terms independent Variables is done under three heads as

- Term related to material of bamboo (X_1)

It clubs the Material terms. (π_3, π_5)

- Term related to material of tool (X_2)

It clubs the tool material. (π_1, π_2, π_4)

- Term related to energy (X_3)

It clubs the energy terms. (π_6, π_7)

After planning of experimentation, the experimental data is collected by measuring with various instruments and its reduction, clubbing and purification is done.

4.6 Measurement of Variables

During the experimental research the data should be recorded precisely, measured accurately and tabulated carefully so that the analysis of data should be proper. The parameters are measured and recorded by respective method or some instrument.

4.6.1 Force Measurement

A load cell is used to measure the force required to cut the bamboo into slices. It is a “Syscon Instruments” make.

Figure 4.1: Load Cell

4.6.2 Time measurement

A stopwatch is used to measure the time required for cutting the slices of bamboo. It is a “Seiko” make.

Figure 4.2: Stopwatch

4.6.3 Energy Measurement

An energy measurement device is used to measure the energy consumption for bamboo cutting. It is a “New India Meter” make.

Figure 4.3: Energy Meter

4.7 Calibration of Instruments

The instruments which are used for the measurement of various attributes and parameters should be properly calibrated to ensure their accuracy and precision. For better and transparent results without any major errors, the instruments are calibrated by comparing it with the standard instruments of same kind whose accuracy and precision is ensured, guaranteed or certified. So each instrument which is used for experimental data collection is calibrated.

4.8 Tabulation of Data

The collected data from the experimentation in the form of proforma is tabulated in a proper manner so that it can be interpreted properly and its analysis can be done.

Sr. No.	Input Variable										Output Variable		
	Tool Hardness, H_T (BHN)	Relief Angle, ϕ	Condition of Bamboo, B_T	Rake Angle, α	Outer diameter of Bamboo, d_o (mm)	Inner diameter of Bamboo, d_i (mm)	Force, F (N)	Velocity, V_p (m/sec)	Input Energy (KJ)	Work Done (KJ)	Production Rate (No. of Slice/sec.)	Quality (degree)	Efficiency, (%)
	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5	X_6	X_7	X_8	X_9	X_{10}	Y_1	Y_2	Y_3
1	260	25	2	0	50	30	122.63	0.53	0.197	0.176	2.21	160	89.35
2	260	25	2	0	53	21	147.15	0.54	0.259	0.226	1.49	165	87.05
3	260	25	2	0	52	25	141.26	0.56	0.238	0.212	1.56	155	89.18
4	260	25	2	0	45	27	117.72	0.54	0.174	0.149	1.55	155	85.91
5	260	25	2	0	45	0	153.04	0.56	0.224	0.194	0.97	170	86.42
6	260	25	2	0	43	0	152.06	0.51	0.207	0.182	0.88	180	87.99
7	260	25	2	0	51	0	159.90	0.56	0.266	0.235	0.96	180	88.12
8	260	25	2	0	53	0	163.83	0.54	0.282	0.251	0.94	180	89.02
9	260	25	1	0	51	30	126.55	0.56	0.212	0.186	1.70	140	87.44
10	260	25	1	0	53	21	147.15	0.56	0.259	0.226	1.49	145	87.05

Table 4.3: Experimental data sample readings

In this manner, as per calculated sample size, all 1296 readings are taken from experimentation and tabulated which are shown in Annexure (I).

4.9 Dimensionless Data

The data collected from the experimentation is in the form of subjective information and dimensional measurements. This data is then converted into the dimensionless terms by using dimensional analysis. The excel sheet is prepared by using the formulae in which the entered data is converted into dimensionless terms. The data sheet for sample size 1296 is taken and the sample reading are shown as follows,

Sr. No.	π_1	π_2	π_3	π_4	π_5	π_6	π_7	π_8	π_9	π_{10}
1	260	25	2	0	0.6000	3.2084E-05	2.8667E-05	209.77	160	89.35
2	260	25	2	0	0.3962	3.3235E-05	2.8931E-05	145.77	165	87.05
3	260	25	2	0	0.4808	3.2345E-05	2.8846E-05	144.27	155	89.18
4	260	25	2	0	0.6000	3.2765E-05	2.8148E-05	129.31	155	85.91
5	260	25	2	0	0.0000	3.2572E-05	2.8148E-05	78.62	170	86.42
6	260	25	2	0	0.0000	3.1714E-05	2.7907E-05	74.14	180	87.99
7	260	25	2	0	0.0000	3.2635E-05	2.8758E-05	87.93	180	88.12
8	260	25	2	0	0.0000	3.2500E-05	2.8931E-05	91.38	180	89.02
9	260	25	1	0	0.5882	3.2891E-05	2.8758E-05	154.93	140	87.44
10	260	25	1	0	0.3962	3.3235E-05	2.8931E-05	140.75	145	87.05

Table 4.4: Dimensionless data sample readings

4.10 Clubbed Data

According to the clubbing and reduction criterion, the data is converted into the terms X_1 , X_2 , X_3 (inputs), Y_1 , Y_2 and Y_3 (outputs). The readings in the form of clubbed data and the sample readings are as follows.

Sr. No.	X_1	X_2	X_3	Y_1	Y_2	Y_3
1	1.2000	0	9.1974E-10	209.77	160	89.35
2	0.7925	0	9.6152E-10	145.77	165	87.05
3	0.9615	0	9.3304E-10	144.27	155	89.18
4	1.2000	0	9.2229E-10	129.31	155	85.91
5	0.0000	0	9.1683E-10	78.62	170	86.42
6	0.0000	0	8.8505E-10	74.14	180	87.99
7	0.0000	0	9.3853E-10	87.93	180	88.12
8	0.0000	0	9.4026E-10	91.38	180	89.02
9	0.5882	0	9.4587E-10	154.93	140	87.44
10	0.3962	0	9.6152E-10	140.75	145	87.05

Table 4.5: Clubbed data sample readings

5.0 Result Discussion and Conclusion:

On the basis of results, conclusions are drawn and also the recommendations are given for future work.

The conclusions are as below:

- Initially progressive die was considered in order to perform all bamboo processing operations namely splitting, slicing and square sticks making but during experimentation due to thickness of tool, slice get stuck-up and processing is impossible. Thus progressive die was failed, hence progressive die is not considered thereafter.
- In mechanical bamboo processing machine initially belt drive was taken into consideration but during experimentation it was observed that due to impact load on a slider it sometime stops which affects quality of bamboo slice. Therefore gear box was installed instead of belt drive.
- During experimentation it is found that because of impact load on tool tip, tool tip wears out for less thickness of tool. Hence tool thickness was increased and tool wear was reduced.
- Initially three motors were taken into consideration namely 0.5 HP, 1 HP and 2 HP. During experimentation it is observed that 0.5 HP motor gives better quality of slice and efficiency of system is high. Hence 0.5 HP motor is recommended.
- Mathematical model is developed considering exponential model for various parameters like production rate, quality and efficiency.
- Mathematical model is developed considering multivariable linear regression for various parameters like production rate, quality and efficiency.

Sr. No.	Output Variable	Multivariable Linear Regression Model	R ²
1	Production Rate	$Y_1 = 1.154651 - 6.2E-05X_1 + 0.000347X_2 - 0.00445X_3 - 0.00196X_4 - 0.02525X_5 + 0.028952X_6 - 0.00284X_7 + 1.165921X_8 + 0.27392X_9 + 3.523711X_{10}$	0.9734
2	Quality	$Y_2 = 167.6668 + 0.191582X_1 + 0.426038X_2 + 15.60331X_3 + 1.563383X_4 + 0.855056X_5 - 0.75497X_6 + 0.085249X_7 - 232.095X_8 + 1.824672X_9 - 51.2326X_{10}$	0.9345

LIBERTE JOURNAL (ISSN:0024-2020) VOLUME 14 ISSUE 5 2026			
3	Efficiency	$Y_3 = 50.04206 - 0.00024X_1 - 0.00666X_2 - 0.0258X_3 - 0.00832X_4 + 0.417884X_5 + 0.02698X_6 + 0.165961X_7 + 3.430931X_8 - 273.891X_9 + 264.7087X_{10}$	0.9749

- Comparison of exponential and multivariable linear regression model on the basis of coefficient of determination (R^2).

Sr. No.	Output Variable	R^2 of Exponential Model	R^2 of Multivariable Linear Regression Model
1	Production Rate	0.2330	0.9734
2	Quality	0.1972	0.9345
3	Efficiency	0.368	0.9749

Based on R^2 value of multivariable linear regression model and exponential model best fit model is multivariable linear regression model.

- Mathematical model is developed considering non-dimensional analysis (club data) for various parameters like production rate, quality and efficiency.

Sr. No.	Output Variable	Multivariable Linear Regression Model for Club Data	R^2
1	Production Rate	$Y_1 = 89.99785 + 67.36053X_1 + 0.000259X_2 + 0X_3$	0.7281
2	Quality	$Y_2 = 158.2556 - 15.5174X_1 + 0.000467X_2 + 0X_3$	0.2823
3	Efficiency	$Y_3 = 76.96177 - 0.93208X_1 - 1.4E-07X_2 + 0X_3$	0.0020

- Comparison of multivariable linear regression model (using 10 input variable) and multivariable linear regression model (club data) on the basis of coefficient of determination (R^2).

Sr. No.	Output Variable	R^2 of Multivariable Linear Regression Model (10 Input Variables)	R^2 of Multivariable Linear Regression Model (Club data)

LIBERTE JOURNAL (ISSN:0024-2020) VOLUME 14 ISSUE 5 2026			
1	Production Rate	0.9734	0.7281
2	Quality	0.9345	0.2823
3	Efficiency	0.9749	0.0020

- After comparing the R^2 values of multivariable linear regression model and club data, R square value of multivariable linear regression model with 10 input variables is more as shown in the above table and hence multivariable linear regression models for 10 input variables are accepted .

References:

- [1] Aniket Baksy, “The Bamboo Industry in India”, CCS working Paper # 283, July 2013.
- [2] Soumitra Biswas and G Srikanth, “Report of Technology Information, Forecasting & Assessment Council (TIFAC)”, New Delhi, Annual Report,2004-05,2005-06,2007-08 on National Mission on Bamboo Applications (NMBA).
- [3] Xiaobo Li, “Physical, Chemical, and Mechanical Properties of Bamboo and Its Utilization Potential for Fiberboard Manufacturing”, M.S. Chinese Academy of Forestry, May, 2004.
- [4] Gnanaharan R. and Mosteiro A.P., “Manual on Processing of bamboo and rattan of International Network for Bamboo and Rattan (INBAR)”, New Delhi, Beijing, Eindhoven.
- [5] Jiang Changzheng, Dr. Yu Gang, “Technical Innovations to Increase the Competitive Capability of Bamboo Products”.
- [6] Carrasco Andrea, Fronda John and MacRae Brian, “Mechanical Properties of Bamboo”, Report of Civil Engineering, Research University of Southern California, Los Angeles
- [7] Hilbert Schenck, “Theories of Engineering Experimentation”, Third Edition, Mc-GrawHill Company, Hemisphere Publishing Corporation, Washington, 1979.
- [8] Manhua Xie, Guangjie Zhao, “Technology of Pigmentation of Bamboo Strips by Carbonizing and Dyeing Treatment”, Beijing Forestry University, College of Material Science and Technology, Beijing, China
- [9] V. S. Godbole, “Related articles on effect of water absorption on the mechanical properties of bamboo”, Cited by 6, 1986
- [10] Arun Bansal, “Bamboo Matchstick Unit”, International network for Bamboo and Rattan (INBAR)
- [11] V. G. Jenner, Md. Selim Reza, “Agarbattis: A Sustainable Bamboo Cluster Based Rural Enterprise Development in Northeast Region of India through P4 Approach”
- [12] Paudel Shyam K. and Das A. N., “Bamboo Research and Development in Nepal”, Journal of Forest and Livelihood, Vol. 2(1), pp 59 to 61
- [13] Chen Sujun, Hu Bao, “Bamboo Product Processing Industry and Income of Bamboo Farmers”, Agricultural Modernization and Rural Development Research Center, Zhejiang University, Hangzhong, Zhejiang, China

- LIBERTE JOURNAL ISSN:0024-2020 VOLUME 14 ISSUE 5 2026
- [14] Jules J.A. Janssen, "Technical Report International Network for Bamboo and Rattan 2001", Designing and Building with Bamboo
- [15] JIANG shen-xue, ZHANG Qi-shenghad and JIANG Shu-hai, "On Structure, Production and market of Bamboo based Panels in China", Journal of Forestry Research, 13(2): pp. 151 – 156 (2002)
- [16] Ian R. Hunter, "Bamboo Resources, Uses and Trade: The Future?", International Network for Bamboo and Rattan (INBAR)", Beijing, China
- [17] Riba Carles R., Perez Roberto R., "A Concurrent Approach to Design of Reconfigurable Machine Tools to Process Bamboo Cooperative Design", Visualization and Engineering, Springer Berlin/Heidelberg Publications, Volume 3675/2005, pp: 210-217
- [18] LI Li, YANG Yongfu, GUO Jianfang, "Technology of Sawing Bamboo Veneer", College of Material Science and Technology, Beijing Forestry University
- [19] Cheng Jung lin, Ming Jer Tsai and Song Yung Wang, "Nondestructive Evolution Techniques for Assesing Dynamic Modulus of Elasticity of moso bamboo (*Phyllosachys Edullis*) Lamina", Jouranl of Wood Science (2006)52: pp. 342-347
- [20] Zhao Renjie, Chen Zhe and Zhang Jianhui, "Technological Innovative Course and Prospect of Bamboo-based Panel of China", Central-south Forestry University, Zhuzhou, China
- [21] Wang Zheng, GUO Wenjing and GAO Li, "Study on Properties of Bamboo and Manufacture Technology of Structural-use Bamboo Board", Research Institute of Wood Industry, Beijing, China
- [22] Chen Qi-bing and Sun Jun-feng, "Studies on technical systems and comprehensive benefits of converting agricultural land into Bamboo in Sichuan".
- [23] Xiao Jianghua and Cao Yonghui, "Implement the Ecosystem Management in Bamboo Plantation to Improve the Synthetical Benefits", Bamboo Research division, Institute of Subtropical Forestry, Zhejiang, China
- [24] Zou Jizhou, "Promote Xianning Bamboo Industry and Develop Regional Economy", Xianning Forestry Bureau, China
- [25] Ajay Rathod and Avinash Kolhatkar, "Analysis of Physical Characteristics of Bamboo Fabrics", International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology, Volume 3, Issue 8, August 2014
- [26] C. S. Verma, V. M. Chariar and R. Purohit, "Cleavage Analysis of Bamboo: A Natural Composite", International journal of Engineering Research and Application (IJERA), ISSN 2248-9622, Vol. 2, Issue 2, Mar-Apr 2012, pp. 1265-1268.
- [27] C. N. Sakhale, P. M. Bapat, M. P. Singh and J. P. Modak, "Design of Experimentation, Formulation of Mathematical Model and Analysis for Bamboo Cross Cutting Operation", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Advances in Engg. (IJMRAE), ISSN 0975-7074, Vol. 2, No. I, April 2010, pp 61-83
- [28] R. S. Kadu, Dr. G. K. Awari, Dr. C. N. Sakhale and Dr. J. P. Modak, "Formulation of Various Mathematical Models for the Investigation of Tool Life in Boring Process using Carbide and CBN Tools", International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEM),ISSN 2319-4847, Volume 3, Issue 3, March 2014, pp. 86-97

- LIBERTE JOURNAL (ISSN:0034-2020) VOLUME 14, ISSUE 5, 2026
- [29] S. K. Undirwade, Dr. M. P. Singh, Dr. C. N. Sakhale, V. N. Bhatwar, V. M. Sonde, “Experimental and Dimensional Analysis Approach for Design of Human Powered Bamboo Sliver Cutting Machine”, International Journal of Engineering Science & Advanced Technology (IJESAT), ISSN: 2250-3676, Volume 2, Issue 5, Sep-Oct 2012, pp. 1522-1527
- [30] C. S. Verma and V. M. Chariar, “Stiffness and Strength Analysis of Four Layered Laminate Bamboo Composite at Microscopic Scale”, Elsevier, 2012.
- [31] Michael J. Richard, “Assessing the Performance of Bamboo Structural Components”, University of Pittsburgh, Ph.D. Thesis (2013).
- [32] C. N. Sakhale, S. N. Waghmare, S. K. Undirwade, V. M. Sonde and M. P. Singh, “Formulation and Comparison of Experimental based Mathematical Model with Artificial Neural Network Simulation and RSM (Response Surface Methodology) Model for Optimal Performance of Sliver Cutting Operation of Bamboo”, Elsevier, 3rd International Conference on Materials processing and Characterisation (ICMPC 2014).
- [33] Anu Maria, “Introduction to Modeling and Simulation”, Proceedings of the Winter Simulation Conference (1997), pp7-13.
- [34] R. K. Bansal, “Fluid Mechanics and Hydraulic machines”, Lakshmi Publications, Ninth edition, 2011.
- [35] S. K. Choudhary, R. D. Askhedkar, J. P. Modak, “Planning of Experimentation to Optimize Performance of α -configuration Stirling Cycle Refrigeration System”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Advances in Engineering (IJMRAE), Vol.2, No.1, April2010, pp. 233-244.
- [36] S. D. Moghe, J. P. Modak, “Design And Development of Human Powered Machine for Manufacture of Lime, Fly Ash And Sand Brick”, Technical Journal of IHPVA, Vol. 13, No.2 (1998), pp.3-7.
- [37] Suman Sengupta and Rathindranadh Maiti, “Modeling and Simulation of Proportional Two Stage Pressure Relief Valve”, Proceeding of 9th National Conference on Machine and Mechanism, December NACOMM, IIT Pawai, Mumbai, India (1999), pp. 87-97.
- [38] P. Orlov, “Fundamental of Machine Design”, 3rd Edition, Mir Publication, Moscow, Vol. 125, 1986.
- [39] J. E. Shigley, “Mechanical Engineering Design”, McGraw Hill, 1st Metric Edition, 1983.
- [40] Paul H. Black and O. E. Adams Jr. “Machine Design”, 3rd Edition, McGraw Hill International Edition, 1981.
- [41] Liu Kekun, “Production Process & Equipment for Bamboo Daily Products”, Proceedings of International Training Workshop on Suitable Bamboo Management & Processing Technique for Small Size Bamboo Enterprises (2000), P.P.: [88–104].
- [42] V. S. Oberoi, “Report of Technology Information, Forecasting & Assessment Council (TIFAC)”, New Delhi, Annual Report, 2004-05 on National Mission on Bamboo Applications (NMBA).
- [43] J. P. Modak and A. R. Bapat, “Formulation of Generalised Experimental Model for a Manually Driven Flywheel Motor and its Optimization”, Applied Ergonomics, U.K., Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 119-122, 1994.

- LIBERTE JOURNAL (ISSN:0024-2020) VOLUME 14 ISSUE 5 2026
- [44] B. D. Shiwalkar, "Design Data for Machine Elements", Dattatraya Publications, Nagpur (India).
- [45] Prashant Bamboo Machine Sales Corporation, Nagpur (www.prashantbamboo.com)
- [46] Wood Masters(India) Machines Pvt. Ltd., Ludhiana (India) (www.woodmasterindia.com)
- [47] C. N. Sakhale et. al., "Design of a Comprehensive Bamboo Processing Machine", IFTToM: PICA- 2006, 11th – 14th July, 2006, Vol. 1, pp.51-54.
- [48] Design Data, "Compiled by Faculty of Mechanical Engineering", PSG College of Technology, Coimbatore.
- [49] Roberta S. Russell and Bernard W. Taylor III, "Operations Management", Fourth Edition, Pearson Education, 2009.
- [50] S. K. Choudhary, "Experimental Optimization of Some Subsystems of Sterling Cycle Refrigeration with Non CFC Gases", Ph. D. Thesis (2010).
- [51] Excel Regression Tutorial.
- [52] R. H. Parikh, "Study of Accident Phenomenon in the Light of the Concept of Biorhythm and Formulation of Approximate Shield Data Base Model", Ph. D. Thesis (2010).
- [53] C. C. Handa, "Developing a Model to Correlate the Success of an Enterprise with Entrepreneurial Qualities", Ph. D. Thesis (2010).
- [54] C. N. Sakhale, "Design and Development of Comprehensive Bamboo Processing Machine for optimum Performance", Ph. D. Thesis (2011).
- [55] R. L. Himte, J. P. Modak, "An Approach to form Field Data Based Model for Roof Bolting Operation in Underground Mine", International Journal of Engineering Research and Industrial Applications (IJERIA), Vol. 3, No. 1 (2010), pp. 51-67.
- [56] S. R. Ikhar, A. V. Vanalkar, J. P. Modak, "Simulation and Mathematical Modeling of a Manual Stirrup Making Activity Using Field Data Based Model", International Journal of Engineering Research and Industrial applications, ISSN 0974-1518, vol.4, Issue No.1 (Feb. 2011), pp311-324.
- [57] Dr. P. G. Mehar "Economic Analysis, Optimization and Parametric Analysis of Integrated Bamboo Processing Machine", JZU - Engineering Science, ISSN: 1008-973X, Volume-26, Issue-4, April 2026, pp 381- 422
- [58] Dr. P. G. Mehar "Validation and Optimization of Experimental Data for Integrated Bamboo Processing Machine", Archeo Sciences Journal (ASJ), ISSN: 1960-1360, Volume 19, Issue 1, 2026, pp 85-103